

Conversion of climate metrics for policy applications

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Abstract. When assessing CO₂ and non-CO₂ climate effects of anthropogenic emissions from transport sectors, e.g., aviation emissions, a physical climate metric needs to be selected. In addition, climate metrics are required to calculate CO₂-equivalent emissions for integration of non-CO₂ effects in legislation or cost-benefit analysis. However, since various metrics are currently in use, it is desirable to have conversion factors available which allow to convert from one metric to another. The widely discussed choice of climate metric is not impeding any further steps, such as cost-benefit analysis or risk-assessments of aviation climate impacts as the here presented conversion factors are enabling an alignment in a downstream process. Here, we establish the relation between radiative forcing, measured in W/m², and any other physical climate metric with the help of the climate response model AirClim. AirClim delivers temporal evolution of radiative forcing and temperature changes for specific emission developments (constant, pulse in 2025, lifetime 30 years, and business as usual). We provide conversion factors for individual non-CO₂ climate effects, which allow to convert to global warming potential (GWP), efficacy weighted global warming potential (EGWP), relative average temperature response (rATR) or global temperature potential (GTP) over three distinct time horizons of 20, 50 and 100 years. For increasing emissions, the point in time when CO₂ effect becomes dominant over non-CO₂ effects, is shifted later in time when compared to decreasing emissions. For constant emissions and 100 years time horizon the non-CO₂ to CO₂ ratios lie between 0.7 and 2.9 depending on the physical climate metric applied. Application of these precalculated conversion factors allows to perform conversion between various metrics without running a climate (response) model.

1 Introduction

Aviation emissions, comprising carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxide, particulate matter and water vapour together with contrails influence the radiative balance of the atmosphere and have an effect on climate (Lee et al., 2021; Grewe et al., 2021). Physical climate metrics (for detailed definitions see Appendix) provide quantitative estimates on the impact that those anthropogenic emissions and effects have on climate. Bringing various individual effects to a common scale by using these uniform climate metrics allows one to provide an estimate of the combined total effects. Such total estimates are required in order to identify to

what extent mitigation strategies potentially could reduce the overall climate effects. The application of various climate metrics allows for an assessment and a comparison of those aviation emissions with respect to their effect on climate (Fuglestad et al., 2010; Peters et al., 2011). For policy applications the total climate effects is often transferred into CO₂ equivalent emissions, which are the amount of CO₂ emissions, which can be emitted to have the same climate effect as the total emissions (Krey et al., 2014). The climate effect is often calculated in terms of GWP100 but can in principle be calculated with each climate metric depending on the choice of metric for the political application. A definition of a physical climate metric for aviation climate effect consists of three basic components: i) the temporal evolution of the considered emissions, like pulse, sustained or scenario emissions, which are at the origin of the induced changes, ii) the climate indicator, corresponding to the induced change in radiation, temperature or mean temperature and iii) the time horizon under which the climate indicator is evaluated. Note that not all combinations might be meaningful for a specific application (Grewe and Dahlmann, 2015). While the impact of the metric choice on the weighting of individual effects, e.g. CO₂ versus contrails, is well understood (e.g. Azar and Johansson, 2012; Borella et al., 2024) the procedure how to choose a climate metric is not generally established. Requirements were broadly discussed in literature and address e.g. fairness, simplicity and consistency with current policy (e.g. Rogelj and Schleussner, 2019; Meinshausen and Nicholls, 2022). Megill et al. (2024) tested various climate metrics against those requirements and showed that only some of the climate metrics were suitable.

Recent research on climate-optimized trajectories has highlighted that aviation induced non-CO₂ effects possess a strong spatial and temporal dependency on the emission location (Grewe et al., 2017; Matthes et al., 2020; Frömming et al., 2021; Engberg et al., 2024), which led to the development of novel methodologies for response functions in order to provide quantitative estimates of climate effects that depend on the meteorological state at location of emission (e.g. Dietmüller et al., 2023). While dealing with such estimates based on local meteorology, particular attention has also been paid on how to represent uncertainties in the quantitative estimates, in order to explore robustness of mitigation options (e.g. Simorgh et al., 2023). Here, one option to explore robustness of results is to estimate climate effects relying on a set of appropriate physical climate metrics (Grewe and Dahlmann, 2015; Matthes et al., 2020; Megill et al., 2024). Borella et al. (2024) also recommended to use a set of climate metrics at least as long as no political decision on the choice of climate metric exists.

The use of different metrics leads on the one hand to very different absolute values and units and on the other hand to a shift in the relative contributions of the individual emissions and effects to the overall climate impact. For example, both, a short time horizon (e.g. 20 years) and an increase in the temporal evolution of the emissions (see i and ii above) lead to a stronger weighting of short-lived effects (e.g. ozone and contrails compared to CO₂), while the use of a longer time horizon and pulse or declining emissions shift the focus towards long-lived effects such as CO₂. In addition, also the climate indicator (iii) affects those relative contributions.

Hence, the objective of this paper is to provide conversion factors which allow to derive global warming potentials (GWP), efficacy weighted global warming potentials (EGWP), global temperature potentials (GTP) and relative average temperature response (rATR) from the radiative forcing (RF) associated to an emission evolution and time horizon (for definition of the climate metrics see Appendix A). Second, this paper provides an overview on the influence of different metrics, distinct time horizon and emission evolution used on the relative importance of non-CO₂ compared to CO₂ climate effects. Third, this

paper presents how the climate mitigation gain changes using different climate metrics for an operational mitigation use case (alternative routing).

60 We first present the methodology for deriving conversion factors for various physical climate metrics in Section 2 relying on the climate-response model AirClim V2.2. The general basis for calculating climate metrics are temporal evolution of RF and induced temperature changes that are presented in Section 3. Results for conversion factors from RF to other climate metrics is given in Section 4. The influence of a change in the choice of metric on the relative contribution of non-CO₂ effects to the overall climate effect is shown in Section 5.

65 **2 Methodology**

The conversion factors between different climate metrics are based on numerical simulations with the climate response model AirClim that is applied in order to determine climate effects induced by specific emission inventories. These calculations of climate metrics for aviation and hence their conversion factors require assumptions on the temporal evolution of emissions and the time horizon and a method to calculate RF that forms the basis for any climate metric calculation.

70 The climate response model AirClim (Grewe and Stenke, 2008; Dahlmann et al., 2016) is described in Sec. 2.1 and we present specific temporal emission evolutions for a given emission inventory as an input (described in Sec. 2.2), in order to estimate the resulting climate effect measured in a specific physical climate metric. How we convert from one metric to another is described in detail in Sec. 2.3.

2.1 Response model AirClim

75 AirClim is a non-linear response model that allows to establish a direct relation between emissions, atmospheric response, induced radiative imbalance and the changes in near-surface temperatures (Grewe and Stenke, 2008; Dahlmann et al., 2016). Based on a set of base simulations with a global chemistry climate model, this non-linear response model allows to estimate the climate effect as a function of geographic position and flight altitude for CO₂ and non-CO₂ emissions. For the relation between NO_x emissions and the resulting ozone RF, as well as the relation between H₂O emissions and water vapour induced
80 RF, AirClim relies on a linearization approach, whereas for all other components the relation is non-linear. In Version 2.2 we updated the temperature calculation from Sausen and Schumann (2000) to that from Boucher and Reddy (2008). The model has been verified against independent model data e.g. based on the REACT4C data set that includes variations of the flight altitude (Dahlmann et al., 2016). AirClim requires specification of background conditions in terms of CO₂ and CH₄ which are taken into account for the RF calculation. Here, we use the SSP245 scenario (Meinshausen et al., 2020). For calculating the change
85 in global near surface temperature the climate sensitivity is needed, which refers to the degree to which global temperature responds to RF. Higher values indicate greater warming from a given RF. As the climate sensitivity differs for different species, the efficacy is used, giving the sensitivity of a climate species compared to that of CO₂. Efficacy higher than one indicates a higher temperature change for a given RF compared to CO₂. Here we use state-of-the art climate sensitivities and efficacies

(see Tab. 1). For PMO (primary mode ozone) no dedicated studies about the efficacy exists. Therefore, we assume an efficacy
 90 of 1.0.

2.2 Emission inventory and temporal evolution of emissions

To calculate the climate impact of aviation emissions with AirClim, a 3D emission inventory is needed. Here we use the
 REACT4C emission inventory (Owen et al., 2011), which is intended to represent global aviation. Nevertheless, the choice of
 emission inventory has no influence on the calculation of the conversion factors per species, as the initial RF has a linear effect
 95 on the calculated metric (see Appendix B). However the relative importance of the individual species is strongly influenced by
 the used emission inventory. Especially for single flight assessments (Dahmann et al., 2023) or other fuels (e.g. hydrogen) the
 ratio between the individual species can be very different. Therefore, the results in Sec. 5, which shows the contribution of the
 individual species relative to CO₂, would change using different emission inventories.

We employ four different temporal emission scenarios that are used in the calculation of the climate metrics conversion
 100 factors including emissions from CO₂, H₂O, NO_x and flown distances (Fig. 1 exemplifies the CO₂-emissions). All scenarios
 start in the year 2025, having all the same emissions in that year. The scenarios comprise a pulse emission (P2025), a sustained
 emission for representing an aircraft usage or lifetime of 30 years (LT30), a constant emission (CONST) and an emission
 scenario with an expected increase following a business-as-usual scenario (BAU) by Grewe et al. (2021).

2.3 Calculation of conversion factors

105 As described above, a climate metric consists of an emission scenario j , a climate indicator and time horizon. Here we use i to
 represent the combination of climate indicator and time horizon. We calculate for each of the four emission scenarios (P2025,
 LT30, CONST, BAU), the five climate indicators (RF, AGWP, EAGWP, AGTP, ATR) and four time horizons (20, 50, 100, 500)
 the climate metric $M_{i,j}(x)$ for each species x . The climate metrics conversion factors $\kappa_{i_1,j_1}^{i_2,j_2}$ describe the conversion of the
 climate metric i_1 to i_2 for given emission scenarios j_1 and j_2 . We define it here as:

$$110 \quad \kappa_{i_2,j_2}^{i_1,j_1}(x) = \frac{M_{i_1,j_1}(x)}{M_{i_2,j_2}(x)} \quad (1)$$

In Sec. 4 we present the conversion for each emission scenario j from RF to i . Note that we choose here the first year of the
 emission ($t^*=2025$) for the RF calculation and since the value is identical in all our scenarios it becomes scenario independent
 and we omit the scenario for the case of $i_2 = RF$. As an example, the unit for $\kappa_{RF}^{ATR20,j_1}(x)$ is K/(W/m²) and any metric can
 be calculated for a given scenario j by using these constant climate metric conversion factors:

$$115 \quad M_{i_1,j_2}(x) = \kappa_{RF}^{i_1,j_1}(x) * RF(t^*, x). \quad (2)$$

If the RF is not available as a starting value, but another metric i_3 with emission scenario j_3 , the RF can first be calculated by
 dividing with the conversion factor $\kappa_{RF}^{i_3,j_3}(x)$ and then the desired metric can be calculated using the conversion factor $\kappa_{RF}^{i_1,j_1}(x)$

$$M_{i_1, j_1}(x) = \frac{\kappa_{RF}^{i_1, j_1}(x)}{\kappa_{RF}^{i_3, j_3}(x)} * M_{i_3, j_3}(x). \quad (3)$$

120 3 Temporal evolution of radiative forcing and temperature change as a basis for climate metric calculations

The physical climate metrics, that are used here to derive the conversion factors (Sect. 4), are calculated on the basis of the RF or the temperature change. For a better understanding of the respective response functions, we first present the temporal evolution of induced RF and induced temperature change.

3.1 Constant emissions - CONST

125 The temporal evolutions of RF associated with constant emissions (CONST, Fig.1) from various species either show an increasing or a fairly constant forcing over the next 100 years (Fig. 2a, left). Notably, short-lived pollutants such as ozone (O₃), contrail induced cloudiness (CiC), and water vapor (H₂O) exhibit a relatively constant RF over time. However, among these constituents, CiC and O₃ emerge as the primary contributors to RF, whereas H₂O plays a minor role under standard conditions, although its significance might be amplified for supersonic flight scenarios (e.g. Grewe et al., 2007; van 't Hoff et al., 2025).
 130 In contrast, methane (CH₄) that includes here a chemical feedback on ozone (PMO) has a negative impact on RF but exhibits an increasing effect over the first 30 years due to its longer atmospheric lifetime of approximately one decade. Conversely, carbon dioxide (CO₂), which starts with a lower contribution compared to O₃, demonstrates a significant increase in RF as it accumulates in the atmosphere over time due to its prolonged lifetime. Notably, after 50 years, the impact of CO₂ surpasses that of O₃, underscoring the importance of long-lived greenhouse gases for longer time horizons. The results agree well with
 135 earlier findings (e.g. Fuglestedt et al., 2010) and basically comprise the current state-of-art.

The time evolution of temperature change resulting from the various climate species due to constant emissions is shown in Fig. 2a (right). The temporal evolution of the temperature change is shifted in time compared to that of RF (left), as the atmosphere needs a certain amount of time to react to the change in RF due to the atmosphere-ocean inertia. The short-lived effects such as H₂O, O₃ and CiC show rapid increase in the first 20 years, followed by an almost constant temperature change.

140 Despite the higher RF of CiC compared to O₃, O₃ causes a higher temperature change due to its higher efficacy, which reduces the impact of CiC while O₃ is slightly increased (see Tab. 1). The reduced warming effect from CH₄ (= net cooling of CH₄) shows a slower increase in the first about 50 years before the temperature change gets almost constant. CO₂, on the other hand, continues to increase over time, as this long-lived gas accumulates in the atmosphere over decades. After about 65 years CO₂ is the dominate contributor to the total temperature change.

145 3.2 Pulse emissions - P2025

For a pulse emission in 2025 the short-lived effects have a very high RF in the first year, but a very low or even zero RF already in the second year (Fig. 2b, left). The negative RF of CH₄ and PMO, on the other hand, lasts for about 50 years. The effect of

CO₂ is initially small compared to the short-lived effects, but persists for a very long time. After 100 years, the effect is still 30% of the initial effect.

150 As the atmosphere needs time to react on the change in RF, the change in temperature is still visible around 40 years after the end of the radiative effect. If the effect persists over a longer period of time, like CO₂, the temperature change increases for the first years before it starts to decrease. The strongest effect for methane is seen after around 10 years, while the maximum effect of CO₂ is seen after around 20 years. While the first 20 years are dominated by non-CO₂ effects, the effect of CO₂ emissions dominates thereafter.

155 3.3 Lifetime emissions - LT30

The impact of lifetime emissions on RF and temperature changes (LT30, Fig. 2) initially shows the same behaviour as that for constant emissions: The short-lived species show a constant RF over the first 30 years, while the RF of CO₂ and CH₄ increases and decreases, respectively. After the end of the emission, i.e. after 30 years, the behaviour is similar to that of pulse emissions, with a rapid decrease in the RF of short-lived effects and a slow decrease and increase in CO₂ and CH₄, respectively.

160 The temperature change over time also initially shows an increase for all species. After the end of emissions, the changes in temperature due to short-lived species fall relatively quickly, while CH₄ shows a slower reduction. The effect of CO₂ initially rises briefly before falling very slowly.

3.4 Business-as-usual emissions - BAU

In the BAU scenario, emissions rise sharply until around 2040, then continue to rise at a slower rate until 2110 and are then
165 assumed to remain constant (Fig. 1). The RF of short-lived species also increases accordingly. CO₂, on the other hand, grows somewhat more slowly, as it only develops its effect over time. As with constant emissions, the RF of CiC remains higher than that of CO₂ over the shown 100 year simulation period. The curves of the temporal evolution of the temperature change of BAU look very similar to those of CONST. However, since emissions continue to increase, the point in time from which CO₂ dominates is only found somewhat later.

170 3.5 Summary on emissions effects

Besides the total amount of emissions and the ratio between the strengths of the emissions of individual species also the temporal evolution of emissions plays an important role (Fig. 2): Emission evolutions with a strong decrease in emissions (e.g. P2025) have large non-CO₂ temperature effects in the beginning, but CO₂ temperature effects quickly start to dominate with increasing time. On the other hand, scenarios with increasing emissions, like the BAU, weight non-CO₂ temperature
175 effects stronger and CO₂ dominates over non-CO₂ effects at a much later year. The temporal evolution of the difference between ΔT from CO₂ and non-CO₂ is shown in Fig. 3. For CONST the non-CO₂ effects dominate from the year 2081 on, while for increasing emissions (BAU) CO₂ starts to dominate about 10 years later. For pulse emissions CO₂ already dominates in 2037. To illustrate this further, we introduce a simple emission evolution metric $EM = \frac{E(t_{max}) - E(t_0)}{t_{max} - t_0}$ that quantifies

the emission change between the starting year t_0 and the year of the largest emission change t_{max} compared to t_0 . Hence a
180 negative (positive) value of EEM describes a scenario with generally decreasing (increasing) emissions such as P2025 (BAU).
Our scenarios are not very complex and hence this simple metric is able to capture the basic behaviour or the emission scenario
well. To better illustrate the relation of emission evolution and the importance of non-CO₂ effects Fig. 4 shows the relation
of the date where the CO₂ temperature equals and then surpasses the non-CO₂ temperature effects as a function of EEM . It
clearly shows the larger the value of EEM , i.e. the more the emissions are increasing in the scenario, the later the date where
185 CO₂ dominate the temperature effects over non-CO₂ effects and hence the more important non-CO₂ emissions are.

4 Conversion factors between radiative forcing and physical climate metrics

Based on the temporal evolution of RF and temperature change, the climate metrics GWP, EGWP, GTP and ATR are calculated.
A description of the individual climate metrics can be found in the Appendix (A). Some of these metrics are defined as relative
metrics and some as absolute ones. Here we sometimes use the relative form (GWP, EGWP, GTP and rATR) or the absolute
190 form (AGWP, EAGWP, AGTP, ATR). The absolute values are used to calculate the conversion factors from RF. In the following
section we provide conversion factors from RF for a given temporal emission evolution (e.g. CONST).

4.1 Conversion factors for CONST

Table 2 gives the conversion factors from RF to the respective metric based on the CONST emission scenario ($\kappa_{RF}^{i,CONST}$ for
the various metrics i). As AGWP is calculated by integrating RF over the time horizon H and CiC has a constant RF, the
195 conversion factor for CiC linearly scales with H . For O₃ and H₂O the AGWP is a bit higher as for CiC as the lifetime leads to
a slight shift of the impact of the first year to the next one. This slightly increases the conversion factor. The conversion factor
of CO₂, CH₄ and PMO is significantly higher, as the RF in the first year is small and increases over time, especially for CO₂.
Since the climate impact of CO₂ does not depend on the emission location, due to its long lifetime, but only on the emission
quantity and the RF is very small in the first year, the impact can also be estimated directly via the emission quantity or the
200 quantity of fuel burnt (see Appendix C).

The conversion factors for CO₂, H₂O and PMO for EAGWP are identical to those of the AGWP, as the efficacies here are
equal to 1. For O₃ and CH₄, the assumed efficacies result in slightly higher values, while the conversion factors for CiC are
significantly lower. While AGWP integrates the RF, ATR averages the mean temperature change over H , which reduces the
dependency of the absolute values from H . On the other hand, the efficacy is included, leading especially for CiC to lower
205 conversion factors as AGWP. The AGTP also includes efficacies leading to lower values of CiC compared to the other short-
lived species. The influence of the time horizon H on the conversion factor is quite small for short-lived effects with constant
emissions as the temperature stabilizes over time. For long-lived species the temperature further increases leading to increasing
AGTP with H . In comparison to ATR the conversion factors for AGTP are higher, as ATR averages over the total time horizon,
also considering the first few years in which the temperature change is small.

210 4.2 Conversion factors for P2025

The conversion factors for pulse emission (P2025) are given in Tab. 3. Due to the short CiC lifetime of a few hours, the radiation effect is only present in the year of emission, while it is already zero in the second year. As a result, integration over a longer period of time does not change the value of the AGWP and EAGWP. Since for O₃ and H₂O a small part of the effect still takes place in the second year due to the lifetime of weeks to months, the AGWP is only slightly larger than the RF in the first
215 year. However, as for CiC, there is no change in the conversion factor for longer time horizons. For methane, the conversion factor is significantly larger than 1, as a large part of the effect only takes place in the years following the emission. However, as the effect after 50 years is very small, the conversion factor only increases very slightly. In contrast, the conversion factor for CO₂ increases even further up to a time horizon of 500 years, as part of the CO₂ emitted in 2025 is still contributing to its atmospheric concentration and therefore has an effect in the atmosphere.

220 While the conversion factor for AGWP is constant over time for a pulse emission, the conversion factors for ATR decrease over time, as they are averaged over the time horizon and the effect decreases significantly over time. Only CO₂ shows a slight increase from ATR₂₀ to ATR₅₀. CO₂ and CH₄ show slightly higher values as the short-lived effects due to the longer lifetime.

The AGTP, which represents the temperature change after H years, shows very low values for pulse emissions. There is hardly any effect for 500 years in particular. Similar to ATR, the conversion factor decreases with increasing time horizon and
225 the values of short-lived effects are smaller than for long-lived effects such as CO₂.

4.3 Conversion factors for LT30

The conversion factors from lifetime emissions show characteristics of both constant and pulse emission scenarios. For a time horizon of 20 years, the values are identical to those observed for constant emissions, since the emission evolution is identical. Trivially, the conversion factor for AGWP for larger time horizons approaches approximately 30 years for short-lived species.
230 While the conversion factors for CH₄ show only a small increase from 100 to 500 years, as the remaining RF is very small, the conversion factors still increase for CO₂, as a part of the CO₂ is still in the atmosphere.

The conversion factors for ATR decrease for the short-lived species with increasing time horizon. CH₄ shows the maximum value for a time horizon of 50 years, while CO₂ shows the maximum for a time horizon of 100 years due to the longer lifetime. The conversion factors for AGTP also show a very similar behaviour to ATR with a decreasing effect over time for short-lived
235 species. However, the maxima of the CH₄ and CO₂ factors are already evident at 20 and 50 years respectively, as they are not averaged over H .

4.4 Conversion factors for BAU

Due to the increasing emissions in the BAU scenario, the conversion factors also rise sharply with increasing H . As with the other emission evolutions, CO₂ and CH₄ show higher conversion factors than the short-lived species, as the RF for the latter is
240 relatively low in the first year.

5 Comparing the contribution of non-CO₂ effects for different climate metrics

As already mentioned in Sec. 1 the relative contribution from non-CO₂ effects to CO₂ strongly depends on the choice of climate metric and this does not only include the time horizon and climate indicator, but also the temporal evolution of the emissions (Fig.4 and Sec. 3.5). In this section first a comparison of the relative contribution of non-CO₂ effects for the different climate indicators and time horizons for the CONST emission development is given as an example (Fig. 5). The figures for the other emission scenarios are presented in the Appendix (D). For this comparison the net climate effect from NO_x emissions (O₃, CH₄ and PMO) are presented.

Note that the exact contribution of the individual species depends on the used emission inventory and the RF calculation that forms equally the basis for all climate metric calculations. However, the general behaviour of the individual species is not affected by this (see also Sec. 2.3). For the REACT4C emission inventory, used here, and the AirClim model used for the RF calculations (Sec. 2), the contributions of CiC and NO_x-emissions are in the same order of magnitude for EGWP, rATR and GTP, while the contribution of CiC is significantly higher for GWP (Fig. 5). The reason for this is the efficacy used of for EGWP, rATR and GTP, which leads to a lower contribution from CiC. The contribution from H₂O emissions is comparably low for all climate indicators and time horizons.

For all four climate indicators, the ratio of the metric values for non-CO₂ to CO₂ gets lower with increasing time horizon. The reason for this is that CO₂ accumulates in the atmosphere over time due to its long lifetime, which means that the CO₂ climate impact is constantly increasing, while the short-lived effects may have an approximately constant impact.

The largest contribution of non-CO₂ to the total climate impact occurs for AGWP, while GTP shows the lowest values. The reason here is that on the one hand the efficacy is taken into account for EGWP, rATR and GTP, reducing the contribution of CiC. On the other hand, EGWP and rATR integrate or average the climate effect over the entire period, while GTP compares the temperature at exactly one point in time. As a result, EGWP and rATR also consider the first years in which CO₂ has only a small effect, while GTP takes these years less into account, leading to a lower contribution of non-CO₂ effects compared to EGWP and rATR.

In order to investigate the extent to which this behaviour also applies to other emission developments, Fig. 6 shows the relative contribution of non-CO₂ effects to the total climate effect for the various climate indicators, time horizons and emission trends. For GWP (stars), EGWP (dots) and rATR (triangles), a clear decrease in the non-CO₂ contribution with increasing time horizon from about 80% to about 30% to 40% is visible. GTP also shows a decrease in the non-CO₂ contribution, but only for constant (CONST, blue) or increasing (BAU, magenta) emissions. For decreasing emissions, as in the P2025 (orange) and LT30 (green) emission evolution, the CO₂ effects are even negative for a time horizon of 50 years, as the atmospheric abundances of the short-lived species have already decayed and only the long-lived negative effects of CH₄ and PMO remain.

If we compare the relative contributions of the non-CO₂ effects for each time horizon and each emissions evolution (same color), we can see, as already seen in the example for CONST, that the relative contribution of the non-CO₂ effects is greatest for GWP and lowest for GTP.

275 A change in the underlying emissions evolution for a fixed climate indicator and time horizon (same time horizon and symbol, but different colors) has a different impact on the relative contributions of the non-CO₂ effects. The two emission trajectories with decreasing emissions (P2025 and LT30) and the two emission evolutions with increasing or constant emissions (BAU and CONST) each make very similar contribution. The highest contribution of the non-CO₂ effects stem for GWP for BAU and CONST. The contributions for LT30 and P2025 are significantly lower, with P2025 making the smallest contributions. This allocation is not so clear for GTP, showing lower non-CO₂ contribution for LT30, at least for time horizon of 50 and 100
280 years. For a time horizon of 500 years, the grouping remains the same, but CONST shows a slightly higher contribution of non-CO₂ effects than BAU.

6 Application / Use cases

The primary objective of this use case analysis is to demonstrate how distinct mitigation options fare in terms of their favorability when different metrics are employed. Notably, we do not delve into the applicability of individual climate metrics to specific research questions and acknowledge that certain metrics may be more suited to particular inquiries than others
285 (Grewe and Dahmann, 2015; Megill et al., 2024). Instead, this study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of commonly discussed climate metrics.

Our scenario focuses on the academic strategy of adjusting flight altitudes using currently available aircraft. We employ the REACT4C emission database (Owen et al., 2011), which offers quantitative estimates for non-CO₂ effects (NO_x, CiC, and
290 H₂O). Previously, this emission database was used to investigate atmospheric composition changes and climate impacts from cruise altitude changes of ±1000 feet, revealing a trade-off between climate effects from CO₂ and non-CO₂ emissions when adjusting flight altitudes. Flying higher results in reduced fuel consumption and lower CO₂ emissions but increased impact of non-CO₂ effects, while flying lower leads to higher fuel consumption and lower non-CO₂ impact (Matthes et al., 2021).

For the three REACT4C emission inventories (base, higher, and lower) we apply the AirClim model in order to calculate
295 the climate effect in terms of ATR100 for P2025. The conversion factors are applied to convert the climate effect back into RF values. These RF values can then be converted into the selected climate metric. Fig. 7 illustrates the change in climate effect relative to the base scenario for both mitigation options across a range of climate metrics.

Our analysis reveals that flying higher tends to result in a higher climate impact, while flying lower reduces the climate effect for the vast majority of climate metrics, except for the GTP500 with P2025 and LT30 emission evolution scenarios,
300 where increasing flight altitude may not offer mitigating benefits and may even exacerbate the climate impact. In contrast, the quantitative mitigation potential varies significantly depending on the chosen metric. A 20-year time horizon yields a mitigation potential of approximately -10% to -12% for flying lower, largely due to the substantial contribution of non-CO₂ effects to the overall impact. As the time horizon extends beyond 20 years, the mitigation potential decreases to 2-6%.

This study demonstrates that using climate metric conversion factors, like here in the REACT4C use case, can help test
305 mitigation measures for robustness and highlights that while the choice of metric affects absolute values, it may not be decisive in determining whether a measure will benefit for the climate or not.

7 Discussion and conclusion

Based on a set of numerical simulations with the response model AirClim, this study presents conversion factors which allow to estimate various climate metrics for emission evolutions based on the estimated RF of the induced perturbation. Conversion factors are presented for the climate indicators AGWP, EAGWP, ATR and AGTP for time horizons of 20, 50, 100 and 500 years and for four different emission evolutions (P2025, CONST, LT30 and BAU). Hence 64 climate metrics were investigated.

The choice of metric primarily changes the relative contributions of the individual species to the overall effect. A longer time horizon shifts the weighting from the short-lived non-CO₂ effects to the long-lived CO₂ effect. The choice of climate indicator influences especially the contribution of the CiC, primarily through the use of efficacy, as the efficacy of CiC is much lower than 1. The choice of emissions trajectory also influences the contribution of non-CO₂ effects. For sharply falling emissions such as P2025 and LT30, the non-CO₂ effects only dominate the overall effect in the first few years, whereas for constant or rising emissions, the point at which the CO₂ effects dominate occurs much later.

Use of the conversion factors relies on assuming a linear response to an increase in emissions. However, in the case of increasing emissions (e.g. in the BAU scenario) an atmospheric situation could be existing when saturation effects become effective. Such saturation effects are not captured in the applied simulation setup in this study.

The values of the efficacies used in this study are still uncertain, e.g. for contrail cirrus an update efficacy was recently published by Bickel et al. (2025), which has been applied here. In case further updates will become available, the presented methodology remains valid and the values presented in this study remain still applicable, they only have to be divided by individual efficacies used (see section 2) and then multiplied by the newly provided updated estimates. The conversion factors for AGWP do not need to be adjusted, as the efficacy is not included here.

Conversion factors depend on which response model is used. The underlying response models represent e.g. the lifetimes of the relevant species and the lifetime associated to the heat exchange between atmosphere and ocean temperatures. A model intercomparison would help to better understand the model dependency of the conversion factors.

This study does not provide conversion factors for aerosol climate effects, as with AirClim the climate effect of aerosols can not be calculated directly from an emission inventory. Nevertheless, for converting aerosol climate effects the conversion factors from water vapour could be used as an approximation, as the lifetime of aerosol perturbation is coupled to the lifetime of water vapour (Roelofs, 2013). It is suggested to use an efficacy value of 1, similar to water vapour as no dedicated simulations are available in the current literature.

We make these tables of conversion factors available in order to enable conversion from one physical climate metric to another climate metric, without running a climate response model. Possible applications of the conversion factors are sensitivity studies which explore robustness of mitigation solutions to the choice of the physical climate metric. Alternatively, the sensitivity of a trade-off situation can be explored with these factors, when one effect is increasing while another effect is decreasing. In such a situation it is important to estimate the total climate effect, preferably by using more than one single physical climate metric. Having conversion factors at hand makes it possible to switch between different metrics without running extensive simulations or redoing all of them if a new metric is chosen. This means that choosing a metric is no longer a barrier, but can

be supported by rigorous analysis. For political applications, all study results can also be converted into CO₂-equivalent emissions using the conversion factors and the table on the effect of CO₂ emissions per emission. The advantage of these conversion factors is that they can also be used to convert the results of models that do not have the option of outputting different metrics into other metrics. For example of the python library CLIMaCCF V1.0 (Dietmüller et al., 2023) that enables the estimate of weather-dependent climate effects from aviation using algorithmic climate change functions (aCCFs, van Manen and Grewe (2019); Yin et al. (2023) are on the basis of two different metrics, specifically F-ATR20 and F-ATR100. However, currently many more physical climate metrics are used (e.g. Borella et al., 2024). To allow a broader usage of such models and a better comparison to other studies, the presented conversion factors from one physical climate metric to another physical climate metric can be used.

350 *Competing interests.* There are no competing interests.

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445 **Appendix A: Definition of climate metrics**

A definition of a physical climate metric consists of three basic components: i) the temporal evolution of the considered emissions, like pulse, sustained or scenario emissions, which are at the origin of the induced changes, ii) the climate indicator, corresponding to the induced change in radiation, temperature or mean temperature and iii) the time horizon H under which the climate indicator is evaluated. In this section we provide the definitions of the climate indicators used in this study. Note that in this paper, we add, similar to Megill et al. (2024), an A to denote an absolute climate metric (i.e. AGWP, AGTP, iAGTP) and use $rATR$ to denote the relative ATR.

The Absolute Global Warming Potential (AGWP) is the integrated RF over the time horizon H (Fuglestedt et al., 2003):

$$AGWP_H = \int_{t_0}^{t_0+H} RF(t) dt.$$

An upcoming new metric is the Efficacy Weighted Global Warming Potential (EAGWP), which is the AGWP, but weighted with the efficacy r_x of the individual species x :

$$AEGWP_H = r_x \int_{t_0}^{t_0+H} RF(t) dt.$$

The advantage of EAGWP compared to AGWP is that it shows a better correlation with the causative temperature change, as the feedback mechanisms are taken into account by including the efficacy.

The Absolut Global Temperature Potential (AGTP) is a single point metric and gives the global near surface temperature change H years after the start of the emission (Shine et al., 2005):

$$AGTP_H = \Delta T(t_0 + H).$$

The Average Temperature Response is the mean change in global near surface temperature over H years (Schwartz Dallara et al., 2011):

$$ATR_H = \frac{1}{H} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+H} \Delta T(t) dt.$$

465 **Appendix B: Linearisation**

As described above, any climate metrics calculation requires as an input the temporal evolution of annual emissions of a species x , which we call here $E^x(t)$, the resulting concentration changes that result from the emissions $C(E^x(t))$ and the radiation imbalance due to those concentration changes $RF(C(E^x(t)))$. A climate metric $M_{i,j}$ with $i \in \{RF, ATR_{20}, etc.\}$ uses as input the time series of RF based on the emission scenario j . In Sec. 2.2 and Fig. 1 we have introduced 4 different emissions scenarios that we call here $S_j^x(t)$. We allow some scaling a^x of those scenarios and thereby obtain the emission evolution for species x :

$$E^x(t) = a^x * S_j^x(t). \tag{B1}$$

The climate metrics conversion factors $\kappa_{i_1, j_1}^{i_2, j_2}$ describe the conversion of the climate metric i_1 to i_2 for given emission scenarios j_1 and j_2 for climate metric i_1 and i_2 , respectively. We define it here as:

$$475 \quad \kappa_{i_2, j_2}^{i_1, j_1} = \frac{M_{i_1, j_1}}{M_{i_2, j_2}}, \text{ and for the conversion from RF to a climate metric:} \quad (\text{B2})$$

$$\kappa_{RF, j_2}^{i_1, j_1} = \frac{M_{i_1, j_1}}{M_{RF, j_2}} \quad (\text{B3})$$

$$= \frac{M_{i_1, j_1}(RF(C(a^x * S_{j_1}(t))))}{RF(C(a^x * S_{j_2}(t)))}, \text{ and by assuming linearity to a first order in the metrics calculation, we obtain} \quad (\text{B4})$$

$$= \frac{a^x * M_{i_1, j_1}(RF(C(S_{j_1}(t))))}{a^x * RF(C(S_{j_2}(t)))}, \text{ and by choosing the first time step } t^* \text{ for the RF calculation, we obtain:} \quad (\text{B5})$$

$$= \frac{M_{i_1, j_1}(RF(C(S_j(t))))}{RF(C(S_j(t^*)))} \quad (\text{B6})$$

$$480 \quad = \text{constant.} \quad (\text{B7})$$

Note that we choose here the first year of the emission ($t^*=2025$) for the RF calculation and since the value is identical in all our scenarios it becomes scenario independent and we omit the scenario for the case of $i_2 = RF$. As an example, the unit for κ_{RF}^{ATR20, j_1} is $\text{K}/(\text{W}/\text{m}^2)$ and any metric can be calculated for a given scenario j by using these constant climate metric conversion factors:

$$485 \quad M_{i_1, j_2} = \kappa_{RF}^{i_1, j_1} * RF(t^*). \quad (\text{B8})$$

Appendix C: Calculation CO₂ climate effect from fuel consumption

Since the climate impact of CO₂, due to its long lifetime, does not depend on the emission location but only on the emission quantity, the impact can also be estimated directly via the emission quantity or the quantity of fuel burnt. As some models do not estimate the RF of the CO₂ effect directly, a simple estimation of the CO₂ climate effect per kg of burnt fuel is shown in
490 Tab. A1. Note, that the values for AWGP and EAGWP are the same, as the efficacy for CO₂ is per definition 1.0.

Appendix D: Relative contribution of non-CO₂ climate effects to total climate effect compared to CO₂

This section shows the relative contributions of non-CO₂ effects to the overall impact compared to CO₂ for the different emission trajectories P2025 (Fig. A1), LT30 (Fig. A2) and BAU (Fig. A3). The curves are very similar to Fig. 5. For each emission evolution a decrease in the non-CO₂ effects compared to CO₂ with a longer time horizon H . The reduction in the
495 proportion of CiC in EGWP, rATR and GTP compared to GWP through the use of efficacy can also be seen in all three figures. Note that the exact contribution of the individual species depends on the emission inventory used and the RF calculation that forms equally the basis for all climate metric calculations.

Figure 1. Temporal evolution of the CO₂-emissions (Tg/year) of the four emission scenarios used in the climate metrics calculation.

Figure 2. Temporal evolution of RF (left, mW/m²) and temperature change (right, mK) of the emission scenario CONST (a), P2025 (b), LT30 (c) and BAU (d). Effects from changes in CO₂, H₂O, O₃, CH₄ and CiC starting from 2025 over a period of 100 years are shown. For a better visibility of the RF results for the pulse emission (b) two in-lays are included that zoom into the first 3 years and into a smaller vertical axis.

Figure 3. Temporal development of the difference between CO₂ and non-CO₂ temperature effects. The stars along the x-axis indicate when the CO₂ impact is larger than the non-CO₂ effect for the different emission scenarios.

Figure 4. Relation between the characteristics of the emission evolution, expressed with EEM and the date where CO_2 temperature effects are getting more important than non- CO_2 effects.

Figure 5. Overview of the shares of the individual climate species relative to the respective value of CO₂ calculated with different climate metrics for the CONST emission development. Here the climate effects of O₃, CH₄ and PMO are shown as total net effect of NO_x.

Figure 6. Contribution of non-CO₂ effects to total climate effects for different climate indicators, time horizons and emission evolutions for the REACT4C global emission inventory.

Figure 7. Relative mitigation potential, identified as the relative difference of climate metrics of general cruise altitude variations (flying higher, flying lower) with respect to the base case utilizing the REACT4C emission database.

Figure A1. Individual non-CO₂ climate effects relative to CO₂ climate effect for different metrics for P2025 emission evolution.

Figure A2. Same as Fig. A1, but for emission evolution LT30

Figure A3. Same as Fig. A1 but for emission evolution BAU

Table 1. Parameter settings for the AirClim simulations

Parameter	Value	Reference
CO ₂ background	SSP245	Meinshausen et al. (2020)
CH ₄ background	SSP245	Meinshausen et al. (2020)
CO ₂ climate sensitivity parameter	0.73	Ponater et al. (2006)
O ₃ efficacy	1.05	Ponater (2010)
CH ₄ efficacy	1.04	Ponater (2010)
PMO efficacy	1.00	-
contrail efficacy	0.21	Bickel et al. (2025)
H ₂ O efficacy	1.00	-

Table 2. Conversion from RF to other climate indicators and time horizons for constant emissions (CONST). The units are years for the conversion to AGWP and EAGWP and $K (Wm^{-2})^{-1}$, for the conversion to ATR and AGTP.

CONST	CO ₂	H ₂ O	O ₃	CH ₄	CiC	PMO
AGWP20	163.22	20.37	20.37	140.66	20.00	140.66
AGWP50	779.96	50.94	50.94	520.41	50.00	520.41
AGWP100	2446.51	101.90	101.90	1176.65	100.00	1176.65
AGWP500	35220.98	509.59	509.60	6371.02	500.00	6371.08
EAGWP20	163.22	20.37	21.38	146.29	4.20	140.66
EAGWP50	779.96	50.94	53.49	541.22	10.50	520.41
EAGWP100	2446.51	101.90	107.00	1223.71	21.00	1176.65
EAGWP500	35220.98	509.59	535.07	6625.86	105.00	6371.08
ATR20	2.98	0.45	0.47	2.81	0.09	2.66
ATR50	8.32	0.60	0.63	6.14	0.12	5.82
ATR100	15.25	0.68	0.72	8.14	0.14	7.71
ATR500	56.31	0.86	0.90	11.26	0.17	10.68
AGTP20	6.60	0.64	0.67	5.76	0.13	5.46
AGTP50	16.09	0.73	0.77	9.70	0.15	9.20
AGTP100	28.08	0.78	0.82	10.39	0.16	9.85
AGTP500	99.75	0.99	1.05	13.27	0.20	12.58

Table 3. Conversion from RF to other climate indicators and time horizons for pulse emissions (P2025). The units are years for the conversion to AGWP and EAGWP and K (Wm^{-2})⁻¹, for the conversion to ATR and AGTP.

P2025	CO ₂	H ₂ O	O ₃	CH ₄	CiC	PMO
AGWP20	15.1263	1.0192	1.0192	10.6318	1.0000	10.6318
AGWP50	29.7877	1.0192	1.0192	13.0968	1.0000	13.0968
AGWP100	46.5486	1.0192	1.0192	13.3563	1.0000	13.356
AGWP500	120.4760	1.0192	1.0192	13.3616	1.0000	13.362
EAGWP20	15.1263	1.0192	1.0702	11.0517	0.2100	10.6318
EAGWP50	29.7877	1.0192	1.0702	13.6218	0.2100	13.0968
EAGWP100	46.5486	1.0192	1.0702	13.8903	0.2100	13.3561
EAGWP500	120.4760	1.0192	1.0702	13.8956	0.2100	13.3612
ATR20	0.3481	0.0320	0.0337	0.2838	0.0065	0.2690
ATR50	0.3690	0.0146	0.0154	0.1898	0.0029	0.1800
ATR100	0.3223	0.0078	0.0082	0.1059	0.0016	0.1004
ATR500	0.2121	0.0020	0.0021	0.0273	0.0004	0.0258
AGTP20	0.4374	0.0090	0.0095	0.2619	0.0018	0.2483
AGTP50	0.3274	0.0012	0.0012	0.0500	0.0002	0.0474
AGTP100	0.2464	0.0008	0.0009	0.0128	0.0002	0.0121
AGTP500	0.1546	0.0003	0.0003	0.0045	0.0001	0.0043

Table 4. Conversion from RF to other climate indicators and time horizons for LT30. The units are years for the conversion to AGWP and EAGWP and $\text{K} (\text{Wm}^{-2})^{-1}$, for the conversion to ATR and AGTP.

LT30	CO ₂	H ₂ O	O ₃	CH ₄	CiC	PMO
AGWP20	163.22	20.37	20.37	140.66	20.00	140.66
AGWP50	643.39	30.58	30.58	380.89	30.00	380.89
AGWP100	1192.09	30.58	30.58	412.82	30.00	412.82
AGWP500	3482.15	30.58	30.58	413.45	30.00	413.45
EAGWP20	163.22	20.37	21.38	146.29	4.20	140.66
EAGWP50	643.39	30.58	32.11	396.13	6.30	380.89
EAGWP100	1192.09	30.58	32.11	429.33	6.30	412.82
EAGWP500	3482.15	30.58	32.11	429.99	6.30	413.45
ATR20	2.98	0.45	0.47	2.81	0.09	2.66
ATR50	7.33	0.42	0.44	5.02	0.08	4.76
ATR100	8.05	0.23	0.24	3.21	0.05	3.04
ATR500	6.09	0.06	0.06	0.84	0.01	0.80
AGTP20	6.60	0.64	0.67	5.76	0.13	5.46
AGTP50	10.54	0.09	0.10	4.00	0.02	3.80
AGTP100	7.69	0.03	0.03	0.48	0.01	0.46
AGTP500	4.65	0.01	0.01	0.14	0.00	0.14

Table 5. Conversion from RF to other climate indicators and time horizons to BAU. The units are years for the conversion to AGWP and EAGWP and $K (Wm^{-2})^{-1}$, for the conversion to ATR and AGTP.

BAU	CO ₂	H ₂ O	O ₃	CH ₄	CiC	PMO
AGWP20	184.70	24.22	24.22	161.47	22.69	161.47
AGWP50	993.92	69.22	69.22	688.17	62.43	688.17
AGWP100	3506.64	159.04	159.04	1789.24	137.63	1789.24
AGWP500	62991.40	938.14	938.14	11743.92	774.46	11743.90
EAGWP20	184.70	24.22	25.43	167.93	4.77	161.47
EAGWP50	993.92	69.22	72.68	715.70	13.11	688.17
EAGWP100	3506.64	159.04	166.99	1860.81	28.90	1789.24
EAGWP500	62991.40	938.1	985.04	12213.67	162.64	11743.90
ATR20	3.31	0.52	0.54	3.15	0.10	2.99
ATR50	10.41	0.80	0.84	7.93	0.15	7.52
ATR100	21.49	1.03	1.09	12.09	0.19	11.46
ATR500	100.19	1.57	1.65	20.64	0.27	19.57
AGTP20	7.63	0.80	0.85	6.80	0.15	6.45
AGTP50	21.63	1.10	1.16	13.88	0.20	13.16
AGTP100	43.99	1.43	1.51	18.45	0.24	17.49
AGTP500	183.73	1.88	1.98	25.29	0.32	23.98

	Const	P2025	LT30	BAU
AGWP20	8.225E-13	7.622E-14	8.225E-13	9.307E-13
AGWP50	3.930E-12	1.501E-13	3.242E-12	5.009E-12
AGWP100	1.233E-11	2.346E-13	6.007E-12	1.767E-11
AGWP500	1.775E-10	6.071E-13	1.755E-11	3.174E-10
EAGWP20	8.225E-13	7.622E-14	8.225E-13	9.307E-13
EAGWP50	3.930E-12	1.501E-13	3.242E-12	5.009E-12
EAGWP100	1.233E-11	2.346E-13	6.007E-12	1.767E-11
EAGWP500	1.775E-10	6.071E-13	1.755E-11	3.174E-10
ATR20	1.504E-14	1.754E-15	1.504E-14	1.668E-14
ATR50	4.193E-14	1.859E-15	3.692E-14	5.246E-14
ATR100	7.687E-14	1.624E-15	4.056E-14	1.083E-13
ATR500	2.838E-13	1.069E-15	3.068E-14	5.049E-13
AGTP20	3.325E-14	2.204E-15	3.325E-14	3.844E-14
AGTP50	8.109E-14	1.650E-15	5.313E-14	1.090E-13
AGTP100	1.415E-13	1.241E-15	3.875E-14	2.217E-13
AGTP500	5.027E-13	7.791E-16	2.344E-14	9.259E-13
RF(2025)	5.039E-15	5.039E-15	5.039E-15	5.039E-15
RF(2044)	7.111E-14	3.094E-15	7.111E-14	8.531E-14
RF(2074)	1.288E-13	2.030E-15	6.841E-14	1.779E-13
RF(2124)	2.057E-13	1.479E-15	4.746E-14	3.313E-13
RF(2524)	5.733E-13	6.878E-16	2.089E-14	1.062E-12

Table A1. Climate effect per kg(fuel) in [W years/(m² kg(fuel))] for AGWP and EAGWP and [K/kg(fuel)] for ATR and AGTP, respectively

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